

1. Methane emission rates, IRRI, 1992 DS.

2a. Methane emission under two N sources. IRRI, 1992 WS.

2b. Methane emission from ricefields under two sources of organic matter. 1992 WS.

application on CH₄ emission. Improved plant and root growth in CH₄-enriched soil layers—as a result of fertilization—will obviously increase CH₄ emission.

Methane emissions were similar regardless of application method (Fig. 1) at rates of 90 kg N/ha in the wet season (WS) and 120 kg N/ha in the dry season

(DS). Differences in fluxes were not significant between additions of (NH₄)₂SO₄ and urea.

When organic amendments are added to flooded soils, CH₄ production and emission are increased by lowering the Eh and providing more C sources. Adding 5 t rice straw/ha increased CH₄ emission tenfold compared with mineral fertilizers (Fig. 2a). Quality and quantity of added organic materials influence CH₄ formation. Green manure incorporation showed higher CH₄ emission than did adding rice straw (Fig. 2b). Green manure has a C-N ratio of 10 compared with 60 for rice straw.

Because organic substrates are added during the preflooding period before transplanting, the initial emission peak may be missed if CH₄ fluxes are monitored only during crop growth. Small differences in sources of C and its fermentation highly affect emission patterns and emission levels. ■

Effect of cultural practices on methane emission

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Cultural and agronomic practices have been developed to suit the physical, biological, and socioeconomic conditions of the different rice-growing regions and environments. While the effects of agronomic practices on rice growth and yield are well-documented, their relationships to CH₄ emission are not well-established.

Water control is one of the most important factors in rice production. Short aeration periods at tillering and at heading may improve yield in irrigated rice. A constant water level is maintained during the growing season except where mid-season drying is practiced. Large portions of CH₄ formed in an anaerobic soil may remain trapped while the soil is flooded. Entrapped CH₄ may be oxidized when the floodwater is drained during the rice-growing season or when the soil dries at the end of the season. But a lot of the entrapped CH₄ escapes into the atmosphere immediately after the flood-water recedes and macropores become aerated (Fig. 1).

Dissolved methane in soil solution

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Methane that is produced but does not escape into the atmosphere remains entrapped in the soil. This entrapped CH₄ may be oxidized, reducing net CH₄ emission to the atmosphere. Determining the amount of soil-entrapped CH₄ is time-consuming and laborious.

An alternative method is to determine the amount of CH₄ dissolved in soil solution. Floodwater and soil solutions at different depths were sampled using porous tubing. About 5-ml samples were collected in 10-ml vacutainers. The samples were shaken vigorously for 30 s and headspace gas was analyzed for dissolved CH₄. Field sampling was done weekly in plots planted to IR72 and treated with urea (low C input) and organic amendment (high C input).

The dynamics of dissolved CH₄ in soil solution over time followed the same pattern as that of soil-entrapped CH₄. A close linear relationship exists between dissolved CH₄ and entrapped CH₄ ($r = 0.916^{**}$). This allows monitoring entrapped CH₄ using the easier measurement of dissolved CH₄.

Dissolved CH₄ remained at very low levels at low C input during the early growth stages (Fig. 1). Organic amendment at high C input increased dissolved CH₄ tenfold (Fig. 2). At later growth stages, dissolved CH₄ started to increase (Fig. 1, 2). The dynamics of CH₄ production rate at affected by C input was similar to that of dissolved CH₄.

Dissolved CH₄ in the floodwater was negligible. The concentration of dissolved CH₄ in the soil solution increased with increasing depth below the soil-water interface. Maximum concentrations were recorded at 15 cm (the deepest layer sampled) (Fig. 1, 2). Methane movement from this depth was hindered by the plow pan, and the lower soil temperatures decreased CH₄ solubility. ■

CH₄ fluxes (mg/m² per h)

CH₄ (μg/m² per s)

Soil-entrapped CH₄ can be released into the atmosphere as a result of soil disturbances, such as puddling, harrowing, transplanting, weeding, fertilizer/pesticide application, and harvesting. Even if cultural practices do not disturb fields, up to 90% of the CH₄ released into the atmosphere is emitted through the aerenchyma of the rice plant.

In a field experiment using micro-meteorological techniques in combination with a tunable diode laser, CH₄ emission greatly increased during

1. Effect of soil drying on methane fluxes. IRRI.

2. Effect of weeding on methane emission from ricefield. IRRI, 1992 DS.

weeding (Fig. 2). The emission declined to previous levels after weeding. Cultural practices may account for 10-20% of the overall seasonal CH₄ emission. ■